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CONTENTS

Through Students' and Lecturers' Eyes: Kazakhstani Medical Students' Needs and Self-Efficacy Beliefs in Learning English

Laura BAITLEUOVA, Aydan IRGATOĞLU & Aigerim ALIAKBAROVA | pp. 1–20

Young Language Learners' Attitudes Towards Writing in English: The Case of First and Second Graders

Gloria VICKOV & Eva JAKUPČEVIĆ | pp. 21–44

Evaluation of Attention Deficit Related to Digital Addiction in Early Childhood: Teachers' Perspectives

Yönem TÜCCAROĞLU & Şebnem GÜLDAL KAN | pp. 45–59

Understanding Technology Use Intentions Among Generation Z English Language Learners: A Correlational Study

Meral YAVUZ KARTAL & Dinçay KÖKSAL | pp. 60–80

Digesting Centralized Curricula in Türkiye: How Literate are English Language Teachers?

Nesli Çiğdem SARAL & Cem BALÇIKANLI | pp. 81–99

Developing a Student-Centered Project-Based Learning Model for English Writing: Insights from ESL Learners

Nurul Fariyah ROSLI, Nur Nabila AZMAN, Nurul Ajleaa ABDUL RAHMAN & Goh Ying SOON | pp. 100–116

A Needs Analysis Study of Novice EFL Teachers' Professional Development in Türkiye

Gizem AKÇOR & Hatice ERGÜL | pp. 117–136

Exploring the Need for Speech and Language Therapy Services in Turkish Schools: A Comparative Analysis

Hava PEHLİVAN & Sevim İNAL | pp. 137–158

NOVITAS-ROYAL
RESEARCH ON YOUTH AND LANGUAGE

Charting the Path to EFL Writing Proficiency: Unleashing Creativity with Flow Charts

Luqman RABABAH | pp. 159–171

Can Scientific Literacy Boost Early Childhood Special Education Teachers' Competencies Through STEAM-Based?

Marwan HAMID & Misnar MISNAR | pp. 172–182

Project-based Learning Through a Culturally Responsive Lens: Enhancing Learners' English Literacy Skills

Yulia Sari HARAHAHAP, Rama RAMADHANI, Dahlia SIRAIT & Nurhafni SIREGAR | pp. 183–193

Psychological Aspects of Teachers' Self-Development and Professional Self-Realization in Ukrainian Higher Education Through Coaching

Vsevolod ZELENIN | pp. 194–214

Artificial Intelligence in Second Language Acquisition: Bridging Gaps in English Education

Ying ZHANG | pp. 215–228

The Impact of Educational Games on Speaking Skills in the Foreign Language Teaching Process

Turkan Mehraj ISMAYILLI, Khatira Mahammad MAMMADOVA & Aysel Alakbar ASADOVA | pp. 229–240

Exploring Linguistic Paradigms in Language Applications to Augment Arabic Language Acquisition

Fawzi ALGHAZALI & Mohammed ALZYOUNI | pp. 241–251